

THE COMPOSITION OF PHRASES IN THE POETRY OF THE KARAKALPAK LITERATURE

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Abstract: Phraseologisms are phrases made up of several words, while forming a little together in the course of distant times during the development of our language. Such stable phrases are distinguished by their soundness, the stability of their meaning, and their style. In the composition of the poem, the historical life of the nation, its wisdom, its perfect spirit, its cultural life, and its past are written. Then, over the centuries, the people have a reprehensible image, and the influence of their language skills is guaranteed. They served as an inimitable national symbol of the language, as a symbol of the country. Now, in this article, we will analyze the changes in phrases in the language of the Karakalpak language.

Key words: Phrases, folk idioms, poetry, composition, lexicon, poetry text, semantics, stylistics.

In our language, there are phrases that are made up of several words, which are formed over time. In today's linguistics, these are called stable word formations or phraseologisms. Phraseology is a part of the lexical-semantic level of language science.

In the composition of a sentence, not only single words have a special place, as well as single words, which convey a single meaning and are composed of several words. The skin of his back is inferior, the stability of his mane is inferior, and his style is unique. In our language, there are a lot of idioms with such vivid, beautiful images, full of expressiveness. They is valued as the cream of the tongue, the essence of the tongue. [1.127] In fact, if in the composition of the left language, the history of the people, the wisdom, the perfect spirit, the cultural life, the past, the present, and the future are reflected, then in the course of the generations, the people will be surrounded by the idioms, sayings, proverbs, and other words. the place of wealth is pledged. It served as a national symbol of the language and a valuable guide in the interpretation of the country. Proverbs, deep-meaning catchphrases, idioms, and many other ready-made phrases in the language have served us well in the process of daily commuting, by filling our thoughts with all the colors of their meanings.

The phraseology of the Karakalpak language stands out as the most beautiful, figurative, few-worded, deep-meaning, impressive ready-made words of the folk language. Historical events of the distant sixties that occurred in the life of the people

"Phraseologisms are the forms of the wisdom of the people, which are made into creamy words. It is very important to keep them in mind.[2.5]

Phraseology has become a special object of study in the knowledge of the Turkish language since the middle of the last century. Famous Turkologists S.K.Keñesbaev and Sh.U.Rakhmatullaevs can be mentioned as important experts in the history of the problem of phraseology of Turkish languages.

On the phraseology of the Karkalpak language, prof. E. Berdimuratov, S. Navrızbaeva, J. Eshbaev, G. Aynazarova, K. Pakhratdinov, Q. Bekniyazov, A. Pirniyazova, B. Yusupova, G. Allambergenova, J. Tánirbergenov were trained in various aspects. We know that phraseologisms are created with the aim of having a strong impact on a person's life in various cases, and as a result of the strong impact, the speech is spoken - the impact of the ultimate thought. The words in phraseologism are closely related to each other from the point of view of grammar and semantics, and they mean the same thing. Only the grammatical structure and grammatical changes of phraseologisms are studied as language units. Phrasemes, as a lexical unit other than grammatical variations, were focused on the analysis of semantic meaning variations.

In lexical units lexical meaning is shown. Phraseological meaning is also taught in phraseological units. Phraseological word does not include polysemy (polysemy), synonymy, antonymy, homonymy, and variation phenomena in the word, and it cannot be included in the class of phraseological units - variations. [3.4].

According to the lexical-semantic character of phraseologisms, they are considered to be very complex phenomena. They are distinguished from other words in the language by the signs of idiomaticity, emotionality and expressiveness. This peculiarity of phraseologisms has been the cause of death in the language for a long time. Emotionality is the subjectivity that is given to the events, actions, and things in the world around us through words.

In this article, we analyze the lexical-semantic variations of the phrases included in the poems of Karakalpak people. For example:

If you shoot, I will ask you to come back to me.

That hammer is like a god,

When you feel that you are a child,

We came flying from a far (p. 28).

Let the ball fly,

Let the flower field be happy,

A bee hangs from the jet,

It is on the far side (page 31).

In the first example given, the phrase "come from the request" means "let him do what he has to do", "come from him", "let him give". In our next example, the phrase "come from him" has been added to the composition of the phrase "ari" and the meaning of what is to be said has been sharpened. Bul jeti kirdan asiw- phrase, which is more than all tests, means six words. In the following rows:

A little light appeared,

Just like a bride

I will be very happy,

When I see your face (page 44)

In this example, the order of "I will be very happy" is changed and This phrase "I will be very happy" means to be familiar, to be happy .

This kind of emotional-expressiveness is more often used in the works of wordsmiths than colorful phraseologisms.

Phraseological expressions became more figurative in the sense of lining, but the words contained in them could not be separated from each other. Such idioms are completely different from idioms in terms of their semantic structure. The words in the composition of

the reason are grammatically united, while the other words have a lexical meaning, so they are figurative in the meaning of the word, and they are formed by the combination of two or more words. Phraseological word in Karakalpak people's poetry; Stay in your mind, stay in your mind (p. 71); Together with happiness, Loved his motherland (p. 31) In these given examples, in the form of "Honey in your mouth" type of phrase, gentleness, sweet words, in the following example, "Be generous" is given. The phrase gives the meaning of "joy". In the phrase "Lightning up", the man from the context came out and sat down in a state of great joy. One of the types of phrasal association are figurative narratives. Figurative narratives describe a vivid, impressive, beautiful image of a specific object or event, or the actions of people. Figurative narratives are created by taking a detailed look at one object and comparing it to another event. Figurative narratives are composed of two free words or more than two words in the context of soft words [5.58]. The scarf in your head, when you go I will be sad (page 163); The yellow nightingale danced in the sky, Your gift boiled in my heart (p. 163); With his all feelings, When the bride came, He felt himself happily (6.37). It is included in the meaning of giving the word. In terms of expressiveness as a lexical unit with a different meaning of phrases, it is possible to describe the expressiveness.

For example, in our language, there is a special structure that consists of two equal parts, and they are called two-component phraseological units. The components (parts) included in the composition of the two-component phraseological units consist of two halves of a parallel symmetry poutine, which are as wide as the edges of a twin.

The same, as a separate structure in the system of two-component phraseologisms, has a lexical-semantic distinction in the form of lexical units with a built-in lexical unit. If we take a look at its lexical structure, first of all, it is similar to the phraseology of other types of phraseology. It was noticed that the definition of the most important words is included in the list of terms. . [4.10]. In them, all the principles of the history of the evolution of the people and the language of the people during the historical periods are described: If it is good, let it be, and if it is bad, let it be published (p. 50);

Don't bother your brother,
don't bother your mother-in-law,
don't bother your husband,
let's be a mature bride (page 45).

In the given examples, the same two-component phrases from poet's p, "Improve goodness, hide badness", this phrase was preserved in the folk language from the beginning, and now it is called "respect your sister-in-law" together with the call of our brides to be gentle, elegant be happy" with the phrasing, shyness has surpassed the approval of good manners.

Changing the tropes in the composition of phraseology increases the effectiveness. A.P. Nazarov, a researcher of phraseologisms of the Kyrgyz language, clearly shows the importance of phraseologisms by saying that "the elements of the phraseology increased the expressiveness of the phraseology and turned it into one of the most important tools of the language." [7.9] Let's give examples of phraseologisms that come in the form of teñew in Karakalpak folk poetry: When your mother-in-law give a present, they will be also happy (p. 41);

Parrot is a beautiful bird, give attention to itself, dressed very beautiful, Everyone love at one's (p. 50). In this example, the word "dressed up beautiful" was used in the composition of the

phrase "to be very handsome" for the purpose of sharpening it. In the next example, one edge of the two-component phraseology "Dressed like a parrot " has remained. In this way, the deformation of the column is visible. Common deformation is a well-known phraseological term meaning the change of the word's meaning. [5.70] The component "Swept on the surface" has been changed to the component "Give attention to itself", but the same meaning has been preserved, only the form has been changed.

In other words, the cream of the tongue is a unit - phraseology that is used in the spoons of the poor people. It speaks of professions and arts that our ancestors practiced, visits to the world of plants, animals, and birds, views of natural phenomena, and stories of existence. These phraseologisms, which sum up the people's way of life, daily life, and behavior, became the greatest wealth of our nation's literary language. Phraseologisms in the Karakalpak language are similar, paired, and beautiful in terms of their meaning and the connection of their components.

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